

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe Phase 3

Report on the second summer school Deliverable D5.2

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

The second ESiWACE3-WarmWorld summer school was held at the conference and accommodation center, Jugendherberge Lauenburg – Zündholzfabrik in Lauenburg, Germany, from July 28th to August 7th 2025. The program targeted Master's and early-stage PhD students in fields like Computer Science, Data Science, Applied Mathematics, Meteorology, and Climate Science with programming experience and an interest in scientific computing. Applications were welcomed from all nationalities, with special encouragement for students from Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITC).

The summer school brought together 30 participants for an intensive programme of lectures and practical sessions centred on two core themes: climate modelling and modern scientific computing. Several partners from both projects were directly involved: IT Center for Science (CSC-IT), Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum (DKRZ), Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD), Technical University of Munich (TUM), Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M), University of Cologne, Center for Earth System Observation and Computational Analysis (CESOC). The training materials underwent pedagogical review by partners from the University of Helsinki.

The summer school was well received, both as a valuable learning opportunity and as an overall experience. Participants expressed strong gratitude and appreciation, describing the program as highly enjoyable, well organized, and exceeding their expectations. Many emphasized the significant academic and personal learning they gained, as well as the opportunity to meet new people and engage closely with lecturers in an open, supportive, and approachable environment.

2. Conclusion & Results

The summer school was organised in accordance with the ESiWACE3 grant agreement, but the WarmWorld project had the primary responsibility for organising the 2025 summer school (ESiWACE3 led the 2024 summer school, which was also co-organised with the WarmWorld project). New training material was developed specifically for the event and the pedagogical review ensured coherence, accessibility, and scientific relevance of the presentations. This training material is hosted on the WarmWorld GitLab repository, where the slides are publicly available. Link to the materials is also provided on the ESiWACE3 webpage: <https://www.esiwace.eu/training-event/#training-materials>

There are two related Key Performance indicators (KPIs): K13 the number of participants, and K15 the percentage of specific groups represented at ESiWACE events. The summer school achieved the following results (compared to KPI targets):

- 30 participants (K13: target was 30 participants);
- 100% of participants were Master's or PhD students (K15: roughly 50%);
- 13 of the participants were women (K15: more than 20%).

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
A1: Transfer and establish knowledge and technology for efficient and scalable simulations of weather and climate across the Earth system modelling community in Europe	yes
A2: Close common technology gaps in the knowledge and toolbox for high-resolution Earth system modelling via joint developments across the European community.	yes
A3: Serve as a sustainable community hub for training, communication, and dissemination for high-performance computing for weather and climate modelling in Europe.	yes
Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable ?
O1: Increase efficiency of weather and climate simulations on state-of-the-art supercomputers.	no
O2: Design tools to close technology gaps for high performance computing.	no
O3: Develop tools to tackle the data challenge of high-resolution weather and climate modelling.	no
O4: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services.	no
O5: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via training and capacity building.	yes
O6: Build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth system modelling across Earth system science and HPC and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives.	yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

Planning for the second summer school started in early 2025 with venue selection, budgeting, and lecturer recruitment. The length of the summer school was set to 10 days, and due to WarmWorld securing additional funding, there was no participation fee. In addition, five travel grants of 500€ grants were offered to partially cover participants' travel expenses. The deadline for travel grant applications was 15 April, the registration closed on 30 April, and the notifications for acceptance were done by 15 May. A more detailed list of participant information is given below in Table 1.

Country of residence	Gender	Career stage	Affiliation
Italy	Female	Master student	Politecnico di Milano
Germany	Female	Master student	Universität Hamburg
Germany	Female	Master student	University of Cologne
Austria	Female	Master student	Universität Wien
Switzerland	Female	Master student	ETH Zürich
England	Female	PhD student	University of Reading
Germany	Female	PhD student	RWTH Aachen
Serbia	Female	PhD student	Faculty of technical sciences, Novi Sad
Netherlands	Female	PhD student	TU Delft
Austria	Female	PhD student	University of Innsbruck
USA	Female	PhD student	Columbia University
Germany	Female	PhD student	Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg
India	Female	PhD student	Banaras Hindu University
Switzerland	Male	Master student	ETH Zürich
Ireland	Male	Master student	Trinity College Dublin
Spain	Male	Master student	Politechnic University of Catalonia
Italy	Male	Master student	Politecnico di Milano
Switzerland	Male	Master student	ETH Zurich
Finland	Male	Master student	University of Helsinki
Switzerland	Male	Master student	ETH Zurich
Italy	Male	Master student	Sapienza University of Rome
Italy	Male	Master student	Sapienza University of Rome
Italy	Male	Master student	Politecnico di Milano
Switzerland	Male	Master student	University of Cambridge
Dublin	Male	Master student	Trinity College Dublin
Germany	Male	PhD student	Max Planck Institute for Meteorology
Japan	Male	PhD student	University of Hyogo
India	Male	PhD student	Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee
Mexico	Male	PhD student	Florida State University
Germany	Male	Wissenschaftlicher Mitarbeiter	Jülich Supercomputing Center

Table 1. Participant information.

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An overview of the summer school is available at the dedicated hpc4climate webpage (Fig. 1), and an aerial picture of the venue is presented in Fig 2.

Figure 1. hpc4climate dedicated website opening page: <https://hpc4climate2025.org/>

Figure 2. An aerial image of Zündholzfabrik in Lauenburg, Germany.

4.1. Training materials

The preparation of the training materials started in early 2025 with topic selection and identification of suitable lecturers and instructors. Based on feedback from the previous summer school, and other HPC-related events (both within the project and more broadly), additional emphasis was placed on increasing the participation of female instructors. The majority of the preparation work was carried out by personnel affiliated with the WarmWorld project, with CSC contributing to the development of training content, and University of Helsinki providing pedagogical review of the training materials.

The academic programme was organised around four main thematic areas:

- **Introduction to climate science:** A concise overview of fundamental weather and climate concepts and processes, including how they are simulated and the current challenges faced by climate models.
- **High-performance computing and software engineering:** This section introduced key parallel programming and software development tools through hands-on sessions using the Levante Supercomputer.
- **Data science:** The ICON model was used to detect meteorological events, supported by Python-based tools for visualization.
- **Heterogeneous computing:** This topic focused on developing applications capable of efficiently exploiting CPU and GPU architectures in modern supercomputers, using the Kokkos programming model to refactor a legacy ICON code component.

The final lecture structure is presented below, and more details are available in the lecture notes ([link provided in section 2](#)).

Date	Title	Lecturers
• 28.07. 14:00-15:30	Welcome	Elina Plesca
• 28.07. 16:00-17:30	HPC Keynotes	Florina Ciorba
• 29.07. 09:00-10:30	Intro to Levante Supercomputer	Georgiana Mania
• 29.07. 11:00-12:30	Intro to Climate Tracy Kiszler, Moritz Waldmann	
• 29.07. 14:00-15:30	Climate models	Hauke Schmidt
• 29.07. 16:00-17:30	ICON Scientific Hauke Schmidt, Moritz Waldmann, Tracy Kiszler	
• 30.07. 09:00-10:00	An introduction to Git workflows	Pradipta Samanta
• 30.07. 10:00-10:45	Parallel Programming Concepts	Georgiana Mania
• 30.07. 11:00-12:30	ICON Technical and first experiment I Claudia Frauen, Florian Ziemen	
• 30.07. 14:00-15:30	ICON Technical and first experiment II Claudia Frauen, Florian Ziemen	

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- 30.07. 16:00-17:00 Climate Science Keynote Ricarda Winkelmann
- 31.07. 09:00-12:00 Intro into ComIn Mahnoosh Haghghatnasab
- 31.07. 12:00-12:30 Event detection with ICON
Vera Schemann, Tracy Kiszler
- 31.07. 15:00-17:00 Guided tour of Levante Supercomputer in Hamburg
Jan-Frederik Engels
- 01.08. 09:00-12:30 Coding challenge 1 description and task organization
Vera Schemann, Tracy Kiszler, Mahnoosh Haghghatnasab, Aparna Devulapalli
- 01.08. 14:00-17:30 Coding challenge 1
Vera Schemann, Tracy Kiszler, Mahnoosh Haghghatnasab, Aparna Devulapalli
- 02.08. 09:00-12:30 Coding challenge 1
Vera Schemann, Tracy Kiszler, Mahnoosh Haghghatnasab, Aparna Devulapalli
- 02.08. 14:00-16:00 Coding challenge 1
Vera Schemann, Tracy Kiszler, Mahnoosh Haghghatnasab, Aparna Devulapalli
- 02.08. 16:30-18:00 Coding challenge 1 results presentations Students
- 04.08. 9:00-10:00 Parallel programming with C++/Kokkos Georgiana Mania
- 04.08. 10:00-11:00 Basics of the Fortran Programming Language
Yen-Chen Chen
- 04.08. 11:30-12:30 Challenge 2: Porting the Energy diagnostics in ICON to C++
Pradipta Samanta
- 04.08. 14:00-17:30 Coding challenge 2
Pradipta Samanta, Yen-Chen Chen, Georgiana Mania, Moritz Waldmann
- 05.08. 09:00-12:30 Coding challenge 2
Pradipta Samanta, Yen-Chen Chen, Georgiana Mania, Moritz Waldmann
- 05.08. 14:00-17:30 Coding challenge 2
Pradipta Samanta, Yen-Chen Chen, Georgiana Mania, Moritz Waldmann
- 06.08. 09:00-10:30 Coding challenge 2 results presentation
Students
- 06.08. 11:00-17:30 Putting everything together? all
- 07.08. 09:00-11:00 Putting everything together? all
- 07.08. 11:00-12:30 Closing remarks & feedback Elina Plesca & all

4.2. Feedback

We collected feedback from participants on various aspects of the summer school and report the average scores below (ratings were provided on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 = poor and 5 = excellent):

- How would you rate your overall experience at the hpc4climate 2025 Summer School? 4,7
- How useful and relevant were the topics covered to your interests or work?
[Introduction to Levante] 3,8
- How useful and relevant were the topics covered to your interests or work?
[Introduction to Climate] 3,6
- How useful and relevant were the topics covered to your interests or work?
[Climate models] 3,8
- How useful and relevant were the topics covered to your interests or work?
[ICON Scientific] 3,9

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- How useful and relevant were the topics covered to your interests or work?
[ICON Technical] 4,1
- How useful and relevant were the topics covered to your interests or work?
[Git workflows] 3,6
- How useful and relevant were the topics covered to your interests or work?
[Parallel Programming concepts] 3,9
- How useful and relevant were the topics covered to your interests or work?
[ComIn Basics] 4,1
- How useful and relevant were the topics covered to your interests or work?
[Event detection with ComIn] 4,1
- How useful and relevant were the topics covered to your interests or work?
[Parallel programming with C++/Kokkos] 4,3
- How useful and relevant were the topics covered to your interests or work?
[Fortran basics] 4,1
- How useful and relevant were the topics covered to your interests or work?
[Porting from Fortran to C++] 4,3
- How engaging and insightful did you find the keynote talks?
[HPC Foundations, Goals & Challenges] 4,5
- How engaging and insightful did you find the keynote talks?
[Ice Matters] 4,4
- How helpful were the practical sessions on:
[Levante supercomputer interaction] 3,9
- How helpful were the practical sessions on:
[Running ICON] 4,2
- How helpful were the practical sessions on:
[ComIn training] 4,0
- How helpful were the practical sessions on:
[Event detection] 4,2
- How helpful were the practical sessions on:
[Porting code with Kokkos] 4,5
- How would you rate the organization of the summer school?
[venue] 4,5
- How would you rate the organization of the summer school?
[catering] 3,0
- How would you rate the organization of the summer school?
[schedule] 4,4
- How would you rate the organization of the summer school?
[communication] 4,8
- How would you rate the organization of the summer school?
[materials] 4,6

In addition to the numerical review, we had some open questions, to which the answers we have collated below.

Which session or topic did you find the most valuable, and why?

Participants especially appreciated the coding challenges, hands-on sessions, and technical talks on topics such as porting Fortran applications, Kokkos, event detection, and modern programming approaches. The keynotes and lectures were also well

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received, along with opportunities for networking and informal discussions during events like the barbecue. Overall, attendees valued the practical, interactive nature of the sessions and the broad range of relevant HPC and programming topics covered.

What was your favorite aspect of the collaborative group work?

Participants particularly valued the collaborative and inclusive atmosphere of the group work, highlighting how people from different backgrounds and experience levels openly shared ideas, knowledge, and problem-solving approaches. Many appreciated learning from one another, seeing diverse perspectives and workflows, and working in supportive teams where everyone contributed and no one was left behind. The balanced group setup, informal interactions, and opportunity to connect with peers and staff made the experience both enjoyable and enriching.

Which session or topic did you find the most valuable, and why?

Participants found the coding challenges, especially the second challenge, to be the most valuable part of the program because they combined theory with hands-on practice and encouraged teamwork, debugging, and real-world problem solving. Many also highlighted the sessions on Kokkos, HPC, and porting Fortran to C++ as particularly useful for their future work with climate models and high-performance computing. ICON and ComIn lectures were seen as highly relevant for those interested in climate modeling, while keynotes, networking events, and career discussions provided broader insight into research and professional opportunities in the field.

What was your favorite aspect of the collaborative group work?

Participants especially valued the collaborative and supportive atmosphere of the group work, where people from diverse academic and technical backgrounds could openly exchange ideas, perspectives, and expertise. Many appreciated the opportunity to learn from one another, ask questions freely, and approach challenges through different problem-solving styles and workflows. The balanced and inclusive teamwork, combined with supportive staff interactions and informal social connections, made the experience both enjoyable and intellectually rewarding.

What could be improved for a potential next edition of the hpc4climate Summer School?

Participants suggested that future editions could include more interactive and hands-on activities during the first days, with additional small-group exercises, practical tasks, and earlier group mixing to help participants engage and get to know each other more quickly. Several respondents requested clearer introductory material and better balancing of climate science and HPC backgrounds, including preparatory reading material, more structured overview lectures, and clearer “big picture” explanations before diving into technical details. There were also suggestions to refine the coding challenges by defining clearer goals, offering different difficulty levels, extending the first challenge, and providing fallback milestones or prepared solutions for beginners. Additional recommendations included improved networking and social spaces, access to lecture slides in PDF format, better internet connectivity, and more detailed coverage of topics such as climate model numerics, ICON, and Fortran/C++ bindings.

Are there specific topics, tools, or formats you would like to see included in the

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Participants expressed interest in more advanced and hands-on HPC and climate-modeling content, including deeper exploration of numerical methods, cloud physics, CFD-style simulations, and simplified climate model components implemented from scratch. Several respondents requested additional focus on HPC tools, supercomputing workflows, Kokkos, large-scale data analysis, and visualization tools such as ParaView, as well as practical introductions to development environments like VS Code remote servers or Jupyter. Interactive formats such as Kahoot quizzes, daily review sessions, and applied forecasting exercises were also suggested, alongside more climate science preparation material for participants with primarily HPC backgrounds

Do you think having a diverse set of lecturers, including only women keynote speakers, added value to the summer school?

Overall, respondents largely felt that a diverse set of lecturers—including women keynote speakers—added clear value to the summer school, both in terms of representation and the learning environment. Many highlighted that seeing women in senior technical roles was inspiring, motivating, and made the field feel more inclusive and approachable, while also enriching discussions through a broader range of perspectives. Several noted that diversity itself—across universities, backgrounds, and viewpoints—improved the experience and lecture quality. At the same time, a few participants emphasized that the value of talks primarily comes from the speakers' expertise rather than gender, and a small number felt there was no particular difference or problem either way. There were also suggestions to further diversify speaker profiles, for example by including more industry researchers.

Anything else you'd like to share with us?

Overall, respondents overwhelmingly expressed gratitude and appreciation for the summer school experience, describing it as highly enjoyable, well-organized, and exceeding expectations. Many highlighted how much they learned, both academically and personally, as well as the opportunity to meet new people and interact closely with lecturers in an open and approachable setting. Several comments specifically praised the effort of the organizers, the quality of teaching, and the supportive atmosphere, including informal interactions during meals and discussions about career paths. There were also a few brief neutral responses, but the dominant sentiment was one of thanks, enthusiasm, and a strong intention to recommend the program to others or return in the future.

5. References

There are no references for this deliverable.

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

No changes were made to the plan. For future events, we will begin advertising earlier to allow more time for registration, particularly ahead of the summer period and Visa application processes. We will also ensure that the given feedback will be reflected in both the event organisation and the training material.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy

The summer school contributes to the EuroHPC strategy by training early-career scientists in the methods, tools and theoretical knowledge needed to effectively use HPC environments in their research. It also provides up-to-date training material to enable independent usage to anyone interested in HPC.

8. Sustainability

The summer school (and the previous one in 2024) was organised in collaboration with the WarmWorld project, demonstrating effective cooperation between different EU projects and organisations. This collaboration helps foster synergies and reduce organisational overhead. The summer schools are an essential instrument for training early-career scientists while also supporting the development of their networks.

9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU).
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

Link to the training material is publicly available at the ESiWACE3 website.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached

None.

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will <i>open access</i> be provided to this publication?

None.

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

None.